

GENERAL CONCEPT OF ADJUNCTION PHENOMENA IN GERMAN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The article analyses various ways of studying sentences and the history of studies of adjoining sentences in German language. The adjunction construction phenomenon is a problematic issue among linguists and has been studied in many languages as a stylistic, i.e., methodological phenomenon. However, in spite of this, some aspects of the adjunction construction phenomenon have not yet been fully resolved.

Key words: adjunction element, adjunction construction, deviation, exclusion, joining, division, extension of thought.

INTRODUCTION

One can get an idea of simple and complex structural adjunction construction thanks to the research work on adjunction element and adjunction construction. The phrase adjunction element was first coined by A.F.Efremov. Adjunction construction is divided into certain parts which are represented as simple sentences that are similar to each other. The term adjunction construction is derived from the French and means to be divided, to divide into parts. By the end of the 60s, the term adjunction construction was widely as well as attentional learned and studied in 3 parts which included:

The structural feature of adjunction construction in compound sentences.

- 1) Their tone-dependent features.
- 2) Sensitivity and methodological features.

By the 1970s, more attention had been paid to the semantic features of adjunction construction, and this field of linguistics began to expand further. This revealed that the adjunction construction was divided into several adjunction elements.

MAIN PART

In German linguistics, this condition is studied as a stylistic phenomenon. The phenomenon of adjunction construction plays an important role in the syntax of modern German. German scholars G. Starke, U. Hoberk, L. Shpiser, and others explain adjunction construction in terms such as deviation, exclusion, joining, division, or extension of thought in speech construction. A review of the scientific literature suggests that the phenomenon of adjunction construction is a characteristic feature of the German language.

Adjunction construction has the following characteristics:

- 1) simple or compound sentences with a pause in oral speech and a full stop in writing;
- 2) through the grammatical and semantic connection of these passages with each other;
- 3) two-part structural component;

The detachment element is distinguished by the expression and description of the main event. The phenomenon of adjunction construction is the fragmentation of the idea expressed without additional expressions. The idea expressed after the point is an additional expression to the main expression in the sentence:

For instance:

1. Ob ich das gelesen habe. Einen kleinen Artikel des Schriftstellers unter der Unterschrift. „Ein talentiertes Büchlein. (L.Feuchtwanger, 75p.)
2. Ein Schock konnte mich noch retten. Eine Frage. Zwei Worte. (A.Seghers, 128p.)

Some adjunction elements also look like incomplete sentences. The sentence in adjunction construction depends on the main descripton, which expresses the idea conveyed by one person and shows the integrity of the data:

For instance:

3. Er lächelte schwach. Ein bißchen ironisch. (L.Feuchtwanger, 173p.)

Elliptical sentences serve to express a syntactic whole in dialogic speech:

4. „Hat dich jemand gesehen?“ fragte sie.

„Ja, Eine ältere Frau“.

„Ohne Hut?“

„Ja, ohne Hut“. (L.Feuchtwanger, 357p.)

According to the semantic property, the grammatical tense meaning of the adjunction elements is the same. Morphologically, the grammatical categories of the verb in the adjunction construction, such as inclination, person, number should match to each other, otherwise it will become an elliptical sentence. It is also possible to replace sentences in adjunction construction, but the grammatical sequence does not change.

5. Zwei Millionen war abgemacht. Mit Ausziehen und einem halbsündigen Gespräch nachher– Zwei Millionen mit Ausziehen und einem halbsündigen Gespräch abgemacht. (L.Feuchtwanger, 129p.)

In adjunction construction, several additional adjunction elements can be added to a single basic expression, in which case the expression in a adjunction construction is amplified by the tone.

For instance:

6. Was hatte ich mir von ihr versprochen? Eine halbe Ablenkung zwischen zwei Arbeiten.

7. Ein neues Kleid. Einen nebensächlichen Dialog in einem Café.

In adjunction construction, the distance between the main expression and the adjunction element can be wide. Understanding the meaning of a key expression is a process that is somewhat complicated.

For instance:

8. Beim dritten Anruf erreichte ich Mortens. Meine Frau hat telefoniert –sagte er. Fast eine halbe Stunde. Ich konnte sie nicht unterbrechen. Über Kleider, Krieg und Kinder. (L. Feuchtwanger, 78p.)

The adjunction element that looks like this increases the expressiveness in the next paragraph and highlights the information in that particular section. Cases like this are more artistic observed in the literature. The features of narrative information narration are broad and varied.

For instance:

9. Ich hatte auch nicht erwartet, aber ich wusste, dass ich es ihr nie sagen durfte. Am wenigsten jetzt. (L. Feuchtwanger, 214p.)

10. Eine Jüdische Familie ist hier, sagte sie dann. „Mann, Frau und Kind.“ Vor wenigen Tagen gekommen. (L. Feuchtwanger, 34p.)

Adjunction elements that come in series are common.

11. Vor einigen Jahren besuchte ich Vater oft, aber in letzter Zeit geschah das selten. Höchstens zwei oder dreimal im Jahr. (A.Seghers, 284p.)

In the process of studying the semantic features of adjunction construction, they are observed to come the first secondary parts of the syntactic structure and then the main part. Based on our observations, we are convinced that the occurrence of the adjunction element function is more common.

For instance:

12. Das haben wir dir alles hochgetragen, sagte ich ihm. Und weißt du wann? An deinem Beerdigungstag. (L. Feuchtwanger, Erfolg, 365p.)

The determinant also plays an important role in the function of the adjunction element.

For instance:

13. Ich zündete mir gerade eine Zigarette an, als dicht neben mir eine Limousine hart an der Bordsteinkante bremste. (L. Feuchtwanger, 65p.)

14. Musst du mich daran jetzt erinnern? An mein elendes Liebesleben und die Einsamkeit eines Mannes im besten Alter? (A. Seghers, 312p.)

If the number of adjunction elements attached to the main adjunction becomes one, it is considered a simple structural adjunction construction. By complex structural adjunction construction we mean a structure with more than one number of adjunction elements connected to the main expression. In order to prove the point, we analyze the following example.

15. Augustin kam. Grüsste mürrisch. Machte ein paar Schritte. (L. Feuchtwanger. „Erfolg“, S.242)

16. Ging an dem Porträt vorbei blicklos (L. Feuchtwanger. „Erfolg“, S.40).

As described above, a complex structural adjunction construction is expressed in the example. Here, three self-contained adjunction elements are combined into a single basic expression. When thinking about the construction of complex structural adjunctions, one should note some of their specific features. That is, here we can also identify the ways in which the adjunction element joins to the main expression in the adjunction construction structure with this complex structure. This can be of two ways:

- 1) Direct connection;
- 2) Sequential connection;

The example above is an example of a direct connection. This is because each adjunction element listed here can be combined into a single basic expression without being related to each other.

In sequence communication, however, we encounter a different phenomenon. Here, if we have two adjunction elements in a adjunction construction, the second element cannot be combined directly into the main expression without the first adjunction element.

This way of joining elements relative to the main adjunction is called sequence. In the examples we are analyzing, the adjunction elements that are attached to the main expression, as we have noted above, can often be attached to a single basic expression directly, independently of each other.

We can prove by the following examples that the elements of adjunction are connected in such a way as to form a single basic expression:

16. Er stand auf, badete, machte sich zurecht, langsam, sorgfältig. Ging auf leisen Sohlen durch Haus und Garten. Nahm wahr, die hebräischen und arabischen Spruchbänder an den Wänden. Nahm wahr, das einer das Glas der Mesuso zerschlagen und die Zistern des Rabbi Canon zugeschüttelt hatte. (L. Feuchtwanger. Die Jüdin von Toledo, S. 386 - 387)

17. Der alte Lechner strahlte. Nahm sein Enkel und Patin Kind, in den verschiedensten Stellungen auf. Machte ihm ein Geschenk, das sich gewaschen hatte. Verkaufte das Haus am Unteranger und kaufte, dafür auf den Namen dieses jüngsten Lechner ein Einfamilienhaus am Rande der Stadt. (L. Feuchtwanger. „Erfolg“, p.747).

These examples also shed light on our above points. Here, two or more adjunction elements are attached to each key expression. Each adjunction element has its own characteristics. Various lexical-grammatical tools are used to expand their structure of these features.

For instance:

18. Er stand auf, badete, machte sich zurecht, langsam, sorgfältig.

19. Ging auf leisen Sohlen durch Haus und Garten. Nahm wahr, die hebräischen und arabischen Spruchbänder an den Wänden.

20. Nahm wahr, das einer das Glas der Mesuso zerschlagen und die Zistern des Rabbi Canon zugeschüttelt hatte (L. Feuchtwanger. Die Jüdin von Toledo, S. 386 - 387)

In our example, the three adjunction elements to a single basic expression complement, define, concretize, and interpret the content of the main expression

independently of each other and without each being related to each other. As for expanding their structure, they will have a different look.

For instance, if the structure of a adjunction element is expanded on the basis of phrases in the form of a complement, the structure of the second and third adjunction elements is expanded on the basis of adjunction elements in the form of a subordinate clause.

According to the method of joining, the adjunction elements are joined to the main expression with and without bonding means. As proof of this, we analyze the following example:

21. Dora los bei der Nachttischlampe zum zwanzigsten Mal den Brief, der aus Monterrey kam. Und sie suchte die Stadt auf ihrer Tochter Atlas. (A. Seghers. „Das Vertrauen“. S. 270).

22. Ich hab mich in Hadersfeld hineingehoben in diese Gruppe für Prämek. Weil es gar nah liegt von Kossin (A. Seghers. „Das Vertrauen“ S. 389).

23. Er sann, wie er ihm helfen könnte. Hatte eine Idee. (L. Feuchtwanger. „Erfolg“, S.229).

In examples 21-22, the conjunctions are joined using *und*, and *weil*. Example 23 describes a adjunction element that is joined without conjunctions, that is, using a direct verb-predicate. In written speech, the adjunction element is detachment from the main expression by a full stop. But some scholars argue that the adjunction element with the main expression is detachment by a full stop, a semicolon, a comma, a dash, a bracket, a plus, a colon. But as far as we know the full stop is put after the completed idea.

Only the dot plays a key role in the Adjunction device event. It should be noted that the adjunction element function can contain not only phrases, but also complete sentences, connected compound sentences, and subordinate compound sentences.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, the use of different adjunction constructions in one way or another certainly depends on the purpose of the speaker or writer. As intonation plays an important role in speech, the phenomenon of adjunction construction gave rise to the process of oral speech. In written speech, the intonation is marked with a full stop. As we have already mentioned, the adjunction element is used to add meaning to the idea and to enhance the spiritual nature of the idea, and the sentences in which the adjunction element is involved are accompanied by a decrease in volume and a slight pause.

It should be noted that the phenomenon of adjunction construction is also common in written speech, and it depends on the individual style of each writer, in other words, the adjunction phenomenon and its various structural groups is a methodological factor.

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